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Employee Affective Responses to Organisational Role Stress: A Study

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Abstract—Stress has become the most important factor in influencing individual efficacy and satisfaction in the modern day occupational settings. This article investigates the most contributing variable for organizational stress variables like; Inter-Role Distance, Role Stagnation, Role-Expectation Conflict, Role Erosion, Role Overload, Role Isolation, Personal Inadequacy, Self Role Distance, Role Ambiguity, and Resource Inadequacy, to which extent these factors consequences job stress is investigated. The sample consisted of 110 officer cadre employees who employed in a large Cement producing company. Employees were administered Organizational Role Stress Scale by Pareek in order to assess the level of stress experienced. The result showed a significant effect of these variables on stress, and the Role Erosion factor plays a major role for causing stress among ten variables.

Keywords: Role stress, expectation, recourse, satisfaction.